

Electrodeposited p-Cu₂O films – role of redox active compounds under photoelectrochemical operation

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Abstract

The p-type semiconducting copper oxides CuO and Cu₂O are of interest for the conversion of solar energy due to their medium wide bandgap. The position of their conduction band should allow for reductive processes in junctions with electrolytes under irradiation. In this work, on Cu₂O, the efficiency of several such processes in competition with self-reduction was studied. Thin films of Cu₂O were synthesised *via* potentiostatic electrodeposition on FTO (fluorine doped tin oxide on glass) from aqueous electrolytes. Deposition parameters (electrolyte composition, electrode potential, temperature) had a great influence on electrode properties (phase purity, preferential orientation). Electrodeposited Cu₂O films were p-type. In junctions with aqueous electrolytes, under electrical bias, cathodic and photocathodic currents passed which increased dramatically when reducible redox compounds were added. The influence of various redox couples (O₂, H₂O₂, methylviologen) and their concentration in the electrolyte on the stability of the electrodes was studied. With the investigated redox couples, long-time experiments showed that oxygen saturated and H₂O₂ containing electrolytes gave rise to constant photocurrents and no alteration of the electrodes was found by XRD.

Keywords: cuprous oxide, p-type semiconductor, photoelectrochemical stability

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1. Introduction

p-type semiconductor / liquid junctions can be used for electrosynthetic reductions under visible (solar) light illumination if they have appropriate bandgaps and band positions. Cu-based oxides may qualify for this task. In this context, CuO and Cu₂O have been investigated, especially in view of photoassisted reduction of water to hydrogen. Photocorrosion remained to be a problem, especially for CuO [1-3].

Cuprous oxide (Cu₂O, cuprite) is a suitable photocathodic material due to its optical properties and non-toxic nature. Bandgap energies (E_g) between 2.0 and 2.5 eV have been reported, a spread which is due to various reasons such as deposition method, deposition potential in electrodeposition, oxygen pressure in physical deposition *etc.*, the discussion of which would be beyond the scope of the present investigation. For a bandgap of 2.1 eV, Cu₂O can theoretically convert 18% of the photons of the solar light to charge carriers and for a bandgap of 2.5 eV, 9%, based on published solar spectra [4]. Cu₂O dissolves below pH 4 [5] and has low stability against reduction to Cu upon operation in a photoelectrochemical cell in the absence of appropriate electron acceptors [6]. This reaction may be hindered in various ways like surface modification using co-catalyst deposition [6], deposition of blocking layers and construction of stratified electrodes including catalysts [6,7] or tuning of crystal facets [8]. As to band positions, especially the position of the conduction band (CB) is of interest, as the potential of photogenerated charge carriers (electrons) at this level would lead to envisaged charge transfer reactions (reduction) of solutes in the case of a junction with an electrolyte. If the potential of the CB is calculated based on measurements of the flatband potential (*e.g.* [3]), it would also depend on E_g , which can vary considerably (see above), but for all combinations of published values of bandgap and flatband potential, a CB potential which is sufficiently negative for reduction of protons to hydrogen was found. This is the reason for the strong interest in this material.

The purpose of this work is to see whether conduction band processes with various electron acceptors on unmodified Cu₂O electrodes can be found and whether such reactions can proceed with prominent photocurrent and electrode stability. Electrodes (thin layers) synthesized *via* electrodeposition on conductive FTO glass are investigated.

2. Experimental

Cu₂O layers were prepared by electrodeposition from an aqueous CuSO₄/lactate bath on FTO substrates (F:SnO₂/glass, TEC-7, Sigma Aldrich) held at 60°C, following a description given in ref. [9]. The bath composition was CuSO₄ 0.4 M, lactic acid (2-hydroxypropanoic acid) 3 M, and NaOH 3.8 M.

The phase composition of the layers was determined using X-ray diffraction (XRD) with an X'Pert³ MRD (Malvern Panalytical) diffractometer. Thickness was measured by profilometry (Dektak XT, Bruker) or by optical interference using a fibre optic spectrometer (Ocean optics) and the program Nanocalc. Surface morphology was investigated using a field emission scanning electron microscope FESEM model Hitachi S-4800, and UV-VIS studies used a UV-2600i UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer (Shimadzu).

Measurements of photoelectrochemical properties were carried out using a three-electrode cell with an Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference electrode and a Pt foil counter electrode. A W-Hal lamp or a solar simulator with an irradiance of 100 mW cm⁻² (AM 1.5) was used as a light source. Phosphate buffer pH 8 and Na₂SO₄ (0.1 M in water or in ethanol/water (50/50)) were used as electrolytes. Nitrogen and oxygen were used for gas saturation of the electrolytes.

PAR, Voltalab PGZ100 (Radiometer), and VersaSTAT4 (Ametek) potentiostats, and Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference and Pt counter electrodes were used. Electrochemical cells were equipped with fused silica windows and had provision for gas bubbling and stirring. A W-Hal

lamp or a solar simulator emulating AM1.5 irradiation (100 mW/cm²) served as irradiation source.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Electrochemical deposition of films on FTO

Electrodeposition followed a method described in ref. [9]. A polarisation curve of an FTO electrode in a CuSO₄ / lactate bath under an optimized deposition temperature of 60 °C is shown in Fig. S1a (in Supplementary Information (SI)). Electrodeposition on FTO was carried out at -0.3 V vs. Ag/AgCl (Fig. S1b in SI) and led to the formation of orange layers. The deposition time was 2000 to 3000 s. Charges up to 1 C were drawn in typical runs on FTO substrates. Films of thicknesses (*d*) up to 2000 nm were deposited on FTO. Typical examples of thickness measurements are shown in Table 1, where *Q* is the integrated charge (C) from which the thickness was estimated using $\rho = 6 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and assuming a Faradaic efficiency of 1. Alternatively, the thickness was measured by profilometry (Dektak) of a scratch, or by optical interference spectroscopy (Nanocalc). Good agreement of the measurements using the different methods was obtained.

Table 1. Thickness (*d*/nm) of typical electrodeposited layers.

<i>Q</i> of deposition (C)	<i>d</i> by <i>Q</i>	<i>d</i> by profilometry	<i>d</i> by optical interference
1.05	737	850	714
2.19	1757	1800	-

3.2. Physical characterisation

a)

b)

Fig. 1. Optical properties of an electrodeposited film. a) measured transmission (t) and reflection (r) spectra, calculated sum of transmission and reflection spectrum ($t+r$) and absorption coefficient α ; b) Tauc plot assuming a direct electronic transition.

Electrodeposited films had a smooth and specular appearance. From transmission (t) and reflection (r) spectra (Fig. 1), the absorption coefficient (α) was calculated using $\ln((1-r)/t) = \alpha d$. A bandgap of 2.5 eV from a Tauc plot (Fig. 1b) was obtained assuming a direct electronic transition. This rather high value seems to be typical for electrodeposited Cu_2O as reported by Choi [10]. Structural reasons as also observed as a function of deposition potential (see below) may be responsible for that. A high band gap of 2.5 eV was also found for Cu_2O synthesized by thermal reduction of CuO [11].

SEM studies of the surface (Fig. 2a) showed a dense arrangement of crystallites and some crystal faces of pyramidal shape (111). Slabs of (200) oriented platelets may be distinguished at higher magnification as building blocks of the pyramids.

Fig. 2. SEM pictures of a typical 1800 nm thick film electrodeposited at -0.3 V vs. Ag/AgCl. a) ... magnification 10000 \times , b) ... magnification 20000 \times .

The presence of Cu_2O was confirmed by XRD (Fig. 3a). Side products (tenorite, Cu) were not found in the diffractograms. SnO_2 Cassiterite peaks were from the substrate (FTO).

The films showed phase pure cuprite. Films deposited at -0.3 V had preferential (200) orientation, in contrast to preferential (111) orientation as found for films obtained at less negative potentials (Fig. 3b) and films obtained by thermal reduction of CuO [11]. Some films were post-annealed in vacuum. These films did not show any improvement as to crystallinity, nor as to photoelectrochemical response, and did not show the presence of Cu (Fig. 3c).

a)

b)

c)

Fig. 3. a) XRD of a 900 nm thick film on FTO. The reference JCPDS lines [12,13] show the peak positions of cuprite, tenorite, copper and cassiterite (S, substrate); b) influence of deposition potential (ED) on the prevalence of crystal planes, c) XRD of a film after annealing in vacuum at 400°C, 30 min.

3.3. Photoelectrochemical properties

3.3.1. Influence of pH and oxygen concentration.

On p-Cu₂O, electrochemical reductions can be carried out. In the following, photoelectrochemical (PEC) properties of Cu₂O electrodes were determined. Cathodic photocurrents appeared under illumination (Fig. 4).

a)

b)

Fig. 4. Current density – potential behaviour of a Cu_2O electrode (area 1 cm^2) under simulated AM1.5 irradiation (chopped) in oxygen saturated solutions. a) in $0.1 \text{ M Na}_2\text{SO}_4$ (pH 6), b) comparison of j - E behaviour at pH 6 and pH 8 (buffered) replotted against the reversible hydrogen electrode (rHE). Inset: open circuit potentials (OCP) in the dark and under illumination for pH 6 and pH 8.

The inset in Fig. 4b shows that the electrodes behaved in the expected way for oxide electrodes, with the open circuit potential under light shifting by -59 mV / pH , corresponding

to an identical shift of the band potentials. Therefore, for comparison, the j - E curves were replotted with reference to the hypothetical reversible hydrogen electrode, rHE. The Cu_2O electrode showed almost twice as high photocurrents at pH 8. Reasons for this may be differences in the efficiency of the electron transfer reaction, experiencing a different surface at the the two pH values, considering the isoelectric point (IEP) of Cu_2O lying at $\text{pH} < 6$ [14].

The reactions responsible for the photocurrents can be i) reduction of cuprous oxide to Cu or ii) reduction of electroactive species dissolved in the electrolyte. In fact, the O_2 content of the electrolyte ($\text{pH} \sim 6$) had a big impact on cathodic photocurrents on Cu_2O , as already noticed at pH 8 for Cu_2O electrodes obtained by thermal reduction of CuO [11]. Fig. 5 shows the long-time current behaviour of photocurrents at -0.5 V vs. Ag/AgCl in an oxygen saturated solution, which showed to be quite stable. However, relatively large dark currents were produced which increased in the long runs. Gerischer [15] invoked interband states for oxygen reduction in the dark. In general, as Memming [16] pointed out, in the case of p-type electrodes, the (dark) current limitation under reverse bias is not very efficient as local high fields at dislocations and kinks lead to thermal activation of minority carriers.

Fig. 5. Influence of oxygen concentration in the electrolyte (pH 6). Electrolyte 0.1 M Na_2SO_4 , oxygen saturated, $E = -0.5$ V vs. Ag/AgCl.

In contrast, in the absence of dissolved oxygen (saturation with N_2), relatively small photo- and dark currents passed. This was due to the absence of reducible species in the solution. The only possible reaction under light and in the dark is reduction of the electrode itself. In air saturated solutions, the dark currents were higher and the photocurrents were significantly higher (results not shown). This has already been noticed by de Jong *et al.* [17]. However, this oxygen concentration (estimated concentration 0.2 mM) was not sufficient to suppress auto-reduction of the electrodes completely, as already after 2000 s of polarization (total charge passed -0.8 C/cm^2) the unwanted presence of Cu was seen in the XRD (Fig. 6, uppermost trace and inset of a slow scan XRD). In oxygen saturated electrolytes (oxygen concentration around 1 mM), as tested in a long run under polarisation and illumination (-1.1 C/cm^2 passed), no alteration of the XRD was noticed (Fig. 6, middle trace). Tests were continued up to 4 hours (reaching a charge of -2.5 C/cm^2 , Fig. 5).

Fig. 6. XRD before, after long time polarisation under light in oxygen and air saturated solution (with inset of a slow scan XRD). JCPDS reference lines from [12,13].

In order to increase the oxygen concentration even more, an ethanol / water mixture (50:50) was used. Doubling of the saturation oxygen concentration was expected using solubility data from the literature [18]. However, there was no further increase of the currents, probably due to establishing charge generation control under the given light intensity.

3.3.2. H_2O_2 as reaction product and oxygen scavenger

The reaction product of oxygen reduction could be H_2O_2 . Small amounts of H_2O_2 have indeed been detected in photoelectrochemical reduction of oxygen saturated solutions in contact with p-CuO electrodes [1]. However, the conduction band of Cu_2O is much more negative, so that H_2O_2 as reaction product, if formed, would be easily reduced, and consequently no H_2O_2 was detected by chemical analysis after the experiments. In fact, photoelectrochemical reduction of H_2O_2 on Cu_2O on Pt has already been observed [19]. With the present electrodeposited electrodes on FTO, H_2O_2 was therefore used as an electroactive species scavenging conduction band electrons. The solution was purged with N_2 so that no electron acceptor was present except H_2O_2 . With 0.1 M H_2O_2 , dark currents and photocurrents were enhanced as in the case of oxygen (Fig. 7). The dark currents were 10 times higher than those under oxygen saturation while the photocurrents were about 4 times higher (compare with the upper trace in Fig. 7 where dark and light currents in an O_2 saturated solution are shown).

Fig. 7. Influence of H_2O_2 as electron acceptor. Supporting electrolyte 0.1 M Na_2SO_4 . Upper trace ... O_2 saturated electrolyte, lower trace ... N_2 saturated electrolyte, 0.1 M H_2O_2 . $E = -0.5$ V vs. Ag/AgCl, simulated AM1.5 radiation.

In the amperometric irradiation experiment, the photoresponse to H_2O_2 did not decrease very much in the course of the long run. The dark current increased (doubled) when fresh H_2O_2 was added (nominally doubling the initial concentration - see event at $t = 12500$ s). The photocurrent (current under illumination minus current in the dark) did not change due to H_2O_2 addition. This shows that dark currents were proportional to the H_2O_2 concentration in the studied range, whereas photocurrents were already maximized in 0.1 M H_2O_2 , which means that with this concentration all photogenerated carriers were channelled into H_2O_2 reduction instead of auto-reducing Cu_2O . The total charge carried through the electrode (end after 27000 s reaction time not shown in the graph) was -43 C/cm². The possible reaction during dark and light periods was most probably H_2O_2 reduction to water. There were no traces of Cu found by XRD after this experiment.

3.3.3. Methylviologen

As a scavenger for conduction band electrons also methylviologen (MV, 1,1'-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridinium) was tested. It has drawn attention due to the possibility of acting as an electron transfer relay to a suitable catalyst producing hydrogen [20]. The redox potential of the cation ($E^0(\text{MV}^{++}/\text{MV}^{+}) = -0.45 \text{ V vs. NHE}$ [21]) would allow it to be reduced by photogenerated conduction band electrons in Cu_2O . However, problems may arise due to adsorption of the MV^{+} radical [22], dimerization, or further reduction to the insoluble MV^0 ($E^0(\text{MV}^{+}/\text{MV}^0) = -1.11 \text{ V vs. NHE}$ [21]) leading to inactivation of the electrode.

Fig. 8. Time course of the current density with 0.1 M MV^{2+} , oxygen saturated, $E = -0.3 \text{ V vs. Ag/AgCl}$. Upper curve: oxygen saturated, $E = -0.5 \text{ V}$. Supporting electrolyte $0.1 \text{ M Na}_2\text{SO}_4$, AM1.5 simulated sunlight.

Fig. 8 shows that in oxygen saturated solutions the photocurrents were considerably higher with 0.1 M MV^{2+} compared to currents in its absence (upper trace in Fig. 8. Curve under oxygen at $-0.5 \text{ V vs. Ag/AgCl}$). However, stabilization with O_2 (reoxidation) was necessary, in order to hinder dimerization or further reduction to MV^0 and association of the latter to MV_n^0 [21]. As MV^{+} can easily be reoxidized with oxygen, no stable product of the photoelectrochemical reaction can be obtained under these conditions.

Fig. 9. Photographs of electrodes after prolonged irradiation in MV^{2+} solution, air saturated. a) front-side, b) backside.

The photographs (Fig. 9) show that when reduced methylviologen was not removed (by reoxidation with oxygen), a whitish layer was deposited (products of subsequent reactions of MV^{+} radicals – MV^0) which blocked the electrode. The backside view in Fig. 9b shows the presence of intact parts of the pristine electrode beneath the blocking layer.

Films obtained from DMSO baths showed similar photoelectrochemical activity as the ones deposited in aqueous baths. This is the subject of a forthcoming report.

Conclusions.

Electrodeposited Cu_2O films were p-type. In junctions with aqueous electrolytes photocathodic currents passed which increased considerably when reducible redox compounds were added. Although run under reverse polarisation, the electrodes did not block efficiently

dark reduction of added electron acceptors. This may be due to interband states and the fact that in the case of p-type electrodes, dark current limitation under reverse bias is not very efficient as local high fields at dislocations and kinks lead to thermal activation of minority carriers.

Long-time photoelectrochemical experiments under fixed bias showed that oxygen saturated, H₂O₂ and methylviologen containing electrolytes yielded high dark currents and photocurrents. After long time illumination, no reduction of the electrodes (formation of Cu) was indicated by XRD when electron scavengers like O₂ or H₂O₂ were offered. With some of the so far investigated redox couples, stabilisation without modification of the electrode was demonstrated.

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Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Author contributions:

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